
A Study on Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction: A Critical Analysis on the Personnel in Catholic Hospitals in Kerala

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Abstract: *Organisational climate is the human environment in which the employees work and it provides a favourable or unfavourable setting for Job satisfaction. This paper is a pre-research discussion based on available literature upon Organisational climate and Job satisfaction in the perspective of prospective study on Organizational climate in relation to Job satisfaction in the context of Catholic hospitals in the state of Kerala, India. The literature survey indicates a positive correlation between Organisational climate and Job satisfaction. However, the variables that determine the organisational climate in a Catholic hospital would be different from other private hospitals. Therefore, there could be remarkable variation in the Job satisfaction derived in such situation. The present study is following a mixed methodology as the quantitative data will provide correlation between the variables and qualitative data would help in objective analysis of subjective experience of the clients studied.*

Key Words: *Organisational Climate, Job Satisfaction, Catholic Hospitals*

Introduction

Organizational climate is the core circle of human environment in the boundaries of which the employees of an organization works. Climate effects each activity in an organization directly or indirectly and is affected by almost everything that occurs in the organization. The survival and growth of any organization is directly proportional to the favourable climate in it. Employees in the organization have to be well conversant with rites, rituals, policies etc. This can only bring sense of belongingness among employees and further help in the growth of organization. Organizational climate is of great significance for utilization of human relations and resources at all levels. Organizational climate has a major influence on motivation, productivity and job satisfaction.

Hospital being a major institution in service sector has significant role in maintaining the positive health of the society. Catholic hospitals work with the motive of caring the sick after the model of the healing work of Jesus Christ, the founder of Catholic Church itself. What differentiate the catholic hospitals from other business-oriented hospitals is the service mission focus. Second to the government run hospitals where free treatment is provided, with minimum or affordable expenses the poor people also get an access to all catholic hospitals.

The study is aimed at analysing the organizational climate and culture in catholic hospitals and the level of job satisfaction of the employee personnel in such hospitals. The research is done among the catholic hospitals in the state of Kerala, India. Different employee stakeholders of catholic hospitals in Kerala constitute the study population.

Review of Literature

Organisational Climate

The organizational climate of the service industry is different from the manufacturing industry and especially in case of a hospital as the end product in curing of the disease of the patient, the entire organization should work with dedication and care. The employees of a hospital are not different from those of other types of organizations. There are factors that influence their job satisfaction. It was found that non-monetary aspects of organizational climate are having strong impact on job satisfaction of doctors in government as well as private hospitals in Andhra Pradesh of India.

As a result of this, issues of organizational climate are becoming matters of interest to both behavioural and social scientists as well as human resource practitioners (Patterson, 2005; Stone, 2004; Gershon et al, 2004 and Anderson and West, 1998). Studies conducted in the Western world on organizational climate found that individuals in a particular work group, level, or organization will have fairly similar perceptions of their shared environment (Kuenzi and Schminke, 2009; Hellriegel and Slocum, 1974). At the individual level, organizational climate has been linked with employee job attitudes such as commitment, job satisfaction, absenteeism, organizational citizenship behaviour and turnover intentions (Kuenzi and Schminke, 2009). Climate has been described as a component of organizational culture which is the pattern of shared assumptions, norms, values, and traditions of an organization that

distinguish it from other organizations (Schein, 1992). Study shows that the concept of climate can be useful in examining the quality of interpersonal relations, structure, and other organizational factors and both individual and organizational level outcomes if care is taken to conceptualize and measure at the appropriate level.

Components of Organizational Climate

Many studies have formulated indicators of organizational climate most of which are related. The indicators identified so far range from six to eighteen dimensions (Litwin and Stringer, 1968). Among these are employees' responsibility, organizational structure, warmth, conflict management, identity and rewards.

Organizational climate has been defined as the "relatively enduring quality of the internal environment of an organization that a) is experienced by its members, b) influences their behaviour, and c) can be described in terms of the values of a particular set of characteristics (or attitudes) of the organization" (Taguiri and Litwin, 1968, p. 27). The climate is the "ether" within which an organization exists.

Climate can be seen as organizational climate or psychological climate. Ekvall (1987) states that the organizational climate mediates in the confrontation between individuals and the organizational situation. James and Jones (1974) say that the organizational climate can be viewed in two different ways: "a multiple measurement-organizational attribute approach" or "a perceptual measurements-organizational attribute approach." Both of these approaches are confounded with organizational structure and processes and the general organization situation. The organizational climate is measured using variables like individual autonomy, the degree of structure imposed as the positions, reward orientation, consideration, warmth, and support. This is also the case in the treatment of organizational climate dimensions presented in Litwin and Stringer (1968) where organizational climate is measured along the following dimensions: structure, responsibility, warmth, support, reward, conflict, standards, identity, and risk. Poole (1985) states that climate seems to be a feature of, rather than a substitute for culture. That is, a comprehensive view of culture includes the organizational climate.

A study by Heidi Bushell (2007) has found that Hart, Griffin et al. (1996) Organizational climate model accounts for at least 16% single-day sick leave

and 10% separation rates in one organization. Other studies support the links between organizational climate and many other factors such as employee retention, job satisfaction, well-being, and readiness for creativity, innovation and change. Hunter, Bedell and Mumford (2007) have reviewed numerous approaches to climate assessment for creativity. They found that those climate studies that were based on well-developed, standardized instruments produced far higher effect sizes than did studies that were based on locally developed measures. Further a large number of other studies confirmed Research in organizational climate such as Sharan (2008), Johannesson (2003), Ganesan (2007) Akhilesh and Pandey (2006), Virmani and Kanchan (2000) explain organization climate its various parameters and its relationship with other factors.

Job Satisfaction

Investigated by several disciplines such as psychology, sociology, economics and management sciences, job satisfaction is a frequently studied subject in work and organizational literature. This is mainly due to the fact that many experts believe that job satisfaction trends can affect labour market behaviour and influence work productivity, work effort, employee absenteeism and staff turnover. Moreover, job satisfaction is considered a strong predictor of overall individual well-being (Diaz-Serrano and Cabral Vieira, 2005), as well as a good predictor of intentions or decisions of employees to leave a job (Gazioglu and Tansel, 2002). Beyond the research literature and studies, job satisfaction is also important in everyday life. Organizations have significant effects on the people who work for them and some of those effects are reflected in how people feel about their work (Spector, 1997). This makes job satisfaction an issue of substantial importance for both employers and employees. As many studies suggest, employers benefit from satisfied employees as they are more likely to profit from lower staff turnover and higher productivity if their employees experience a high level of job satisfaction. However, employees should also 'be happy in their work, given the amount of time they have to devote to it throughout their working lives' (Nguyen, Taylor and Bradley, 2003a).

Job satisfaction is simply how people feel about their jobs and different aspects of their jobs. It is the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs. According to Specters, (2007), an alternative approach is that proposed by Sousa-Pose and Sousa-Pose, based on the

assumption that there are basic and universal human needs, and that, if an individual's needs are fulfilled in their current situation, then that individual will be happy. This framework postulates that job satisfaction depends on the balance between work-role inputs - such as education, working time, effort- and work-role outputs - wages, fringe benefits, status, working conditions, intrinsic aspects of the job. If work-role outputs ('pleasures') increase relative to work-role inputs ('pains'), then job satisfaction will increase (Sousa-Pose and Sousa-Pose, 2000).

Perceived support by employees and superiors in the workplace can create a positive organizational climate that relates strongly to job satisfaction (Pritchard and Karasick, 1973; Siegel et al., 2014).

It was observed that people with a high professional background and official employment had a stronger organizational climate scores, so as higher organizational commitment scores. In the study of Gemlik et al. personnel with higher work experience had a greater commitment to the organization. According to Grover et al. age and work experience had a significant impact on job satisfaction and commitment of individuals. People who have been working for a long time in an organization may lose their confidence, thereafter which the feeling will increase the level of commitment of people and cause them to stay in the same organization to maintain their status. On the other hand, in the study of Marmaya et al. individuals with higher commitment to their organizations experience more stress than those with less commitment.

Sharma. M., et.al. (2012) conducted a cross-sectional study by using comprehensive customized questionnaire among Indian physicians to assess the level of satisfaction from their job and also to identify the factors influencing it. A total of 170 physicians were selected from two medical institutes using multistage sampling method. Fifteen facets of job satisfaction were studied with 42 questions. The results of this study showed that about 74% of physicians were satisfied from their job. Physical work conditions, freedom to choose desired method of working, attitude of fellow workers, recognition for good work, attitude of immediate boss, rate of pay, opportunity to use abilities, inter and intra departmental management, attention paid to the suggestions were the nine factors significantly associated with job satisfaction of physicians. According to author the pattern of high proportion of satisfaction of the Indian physicians reported was similar to the physicians' satisfaction working particularly in developed countries.

The above literature shows that there is a relationship between the variables of organization climate and job satisfaction. However, in the context of the catholic hospitals in Kerala that retains a special climate, the job satisfaction need to be studied, because you find employees prefer to work in such hospitals irrespective of comparatively low remuneration. It would be interesting to find out the factors contributing the retention of personnel in such a climate. Hence the study is relevant.

Objectives and Scope of the Study

General Objective

To make a study upon the impact of organizational climate upon the job satisfaction of the personnel management staff in the catholic hospitals in the state of Kerala

Specific Objectives

1. To assess and analyse the organizational climate of catholic hospitals in Kerala
2. To document and explain the level of job satisfaction of personnel in the catholic hospitals in Kerala.
3. To find the relationship between the organizational climate and job satisfaction
4. To analyse the managerial efforts to improve the organizational climate in the catholic hospitals in Kerala

Scope of the Study

Organizational climate and job satisfaction have become a major topic of discussion in India as a result of globalization of the economy and emerging work culture that utilizes maximum productivity of the employees at the threat of personal life. The hefty remuneration, prospective hike in the job ladder and added incentives may force the worker to spend long hours to achieve the target often neglecting the personal life. The hospital setting again demands increased working hours and very often in non-profit sector at remuneration which is not attractive. Then does the organization climate give sufficient job satisfaction is something to be researched.

The study is an attempt to find out how much the Organizational climate in catholic hospitals in Kerala give job satisfaction to its employees.

Methodology and Research Design

The paper is upon the research topic, “A study on Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction: A critical analysis on the personnel in catholic hospitals in Kerala”.

Methodology used is both quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative data for accuracy of the problem analysed and qualitative case study method to get the objective experience of the personnel studied. The universe to be considered for the study would be the employees in catholic hospitals in Kerala having more than 500 bed strength.

Stratified random sampling method in which 100 each from different categories such as nurses, doctors, paramedical staff, administrative and ancillary staff, constituting total of 1000 samples from 10 major catholic hospitals in Kerala having more than 500 bed strength are chosen for quantitative data and 10 to 15 each samples from each selected catholic hospitals are chosen for focused group discussion for qualitative analysis.

The quantitative data would give sufficient input regarding the number of personnel in Catholic hospitals having different levels of job satisfaction as per the variation of the organizational climate. However qualitative data will provide more accurate picture of the job satisfaction based on the subjective experience of the personnel.

Pre-research Discussion

According to Qasim, Cheema and Syed (2012), Job satisfaction is the feeling that individuals have about their jobs. It is also seen as “a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one job or job experience” (Locke, 1976 p. 1304). It is a feeling of accomplishment when once job meets his or her desired expectation. Organizational behaviour literature has revealed that individuals who express high feelings of job satisfaction are likely to exhibit productive behaviours, job involvement and commit to their organizations. Organizational climate has profound impact on the work behaviour of employees in organizations (Metle, 2001; Afolabi, 2005). Many factors affect the satisfaction of employees at their work places and supervisor behaviour is one of them. As cited by Holloway (2012), a study conducted by Momeni (2009) concluded that a leader’s behaviour has a great influence on employees’ attitudes, behaviours, emotions, morale, and perceptions.

Job satisfaction as an organizational phenomenon is multi-faceted (Xie and Johns, 2000; Fisher and Locke, 1992) and as such influenced by many factors like salary, working environment, autonomy, relationships, and organizational commitment (Lane, Esser, Holte and Anne, 2010; Vidal, Valle and Aragón, 2007; Fisher and Locke, 1992; Xie and Johns, 2000). Herzberg's two factor theory recognized these as hygiene factors. This dimension of the theory means factors whose presence or existence create dissatisfaction to employees. However, the lack of it does not bring job satisfaction to employees either. The other factor, motivation factors are rather the organizational practices which influence employees' job satisfaction (Judge et al, 2001 and Luthans, 2002). From a theoretical front, a lot of frameworks have been developed with regards to this organizational phenomenon.

Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

The concept of organizational climate has been studied by a number of researchers. According to Al-Shammari (1992), there are a lot of debates regarding the relationship between organizational climate and job satisfaction. In most of the studies conducted, there have been different dimensions used. As a result of these variations in the dimensions, the outcome of the relationship between these two variables, organizational climate and job satisfaction have also received many varying results (Patterson et al. 2005 as cited in Goi, 2013).

In the context of the current study the relationship between Organisational climate and Job satisfaction is studied in Catholic hospitals in Kerala. Social service orientation or contemporary social entrepreneurship characteristic is a remarkable feature of these service sector firms. However hardly any demarcation between volunteer service and paid service is being done in these hospitals. Hence poorly paid employees may negatively contribute to job satisfaction in these sectors.

Conclusion

The organizational climate is a vast and growing subject. Although job satisfaction is an age-old subject in the context of Catholic hospitals in Kerala it is relevant and will give significant results that could be contributed for the innovation in the organizational climate in such institutions. The findings of this study would hopefully contribute to the organizational development strategies and policy making of the firms in the days to come.

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